

Response of rainfed rice to nitrogen level and postplanting soil management practices

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We studied the response of rainfed rice to 0, 20, 40, and 60 kg N/ha under uncompacted interrow soil (C_0 : 1.36 g/cm³ bulk density) and compacted interrow soil (C : 1.6 g/cm³ bulk density). Soil was a loamy sand with 0.44% organic C and saturated hydraulic conductivity of 45 mm/h. VRS163-2-3 was sown at 23-cm row spacing on 28 Jun 1985 with 18 kg P and 33 kg K/ha. Compaction was imposed after complete crop emergence.

Increasing N levels raised yields in general. Compacting soil to a bulk density of 1.6 g/cm³ raised yields by about 15% (see figure). Straw yields did not differ significantly.

Simple linear regression equations (a) $\hat{Y} = 2.19 + 0.014 X$ ($r = 0.98^{**}$) for uncompacted soil and (b) $\hat{Y} = 2.50 + 0.017 X$ ($r = 0.93^{**}$) for compacted soil, correlating rice grain yield and N application, show a higher response under soil compaction. That can be attributed to more water retention and less leaching losses in compacted than in uncompacted soils. □

Grain yield (t/ha)

Yields under varying N levels with and without soil compaction. Almora, India.

Integrated nitrogen management for lowland rice

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An integrated approach or complete substitution of chemical N with bio-organic N sources would help increase lowland rice productivity. We experimented with azolla and *Sesbania aculeata* alone and in combination with chemical N during the 1982-83 and 1983-84 wet seasons.

The loam soil had pH 7.6, 2% organic C, and 0.21% total N. Each treatment received 17 kg P and 33 kg K/ha. Zn was sprayed at 60 and 90 d after transplanting.

Yields with *Azolla* incorporation at 45 kg N/ha + 45 kg chemical N/ha, *S. aculeata* as green manure at 60 kg N/ha + *Azolla* inoculation at 30 kg N/ha in 1982-83 and 1983-84, and *Azolla* inoculation at 30 kg N/ha + 30 kg chemical N/ha in 1983-84 equaled yields with prilled urea at 90 kg N/ha (see table). N uptake showed a similar trend.

The lower grain yield in 1983-84 was due to low plant population, dry matter production, and panicle numbers. In 1983-84, low dry matter production resulted in low N uptake.

These results suggest that during the wet season, *S. aculeata* green manuring + *Azolla* inoculation or *Azolla* incorporation or inoculation + chemical N can be substituted for chemical N alone. □

Yield and N uptake with bio-organics alone or in combination with chemical N.^a Pantnagar, India, 1982-83 and 1983-84 wet season.

Treatment ^b	Grain yield (t/ha)		N uptake (kg/ha)	
	1982-83	1983-84	1982-83	1983-84
Control	2.7	2.5	47.3	46.3
S 30 kg N + PU 30 kg N	3.4 d	3.0 c	68.2 b	61.9 cd
A 30 kg N + PU 30 kg N	3.5 cd	3.6 ab	70.6 b	71.0 bc
PU 60 kg N	3.3 d	3.0 c	64.0 b	59.0 d
S 45 kg N + PU 45 kg N	4.7 a	3.5 ab	102.5 a	17.8 ab
A 45 kg N + PU 45 kg N	4.6 a	3.7 a	104.9 a	78.8 ab
PU 90 kg N	4.3 ab	3.6 ab	96.3 a	78.5 ab
S 60 kg N + AI 30 kg N	4.7 a	3.6 ab	103.7 a	83.8 a
USG 30 kg N + AI 30 kg N	4.0 abc	3.6 ab	82.3	79.9 ab
PU 30 kg N + AI 30 kg N	3.5 cd	3.5 ab	69.7 b	72.8 b
CD at 5%	0.5	0.6	7.4	10.6

^aValues followed by the same letter do not differ significantly. ^bS = *Sesbania aculeata* green manure, PU = prilled urea, A = *Azolla* incorporation, AI = *Azolla* inoculation at 7 d after transplanting (DT), USG = urea supergranules placed at 10-cm depth at 7 DT.

Slow-release urea fertilizers in sodic soils

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Volatilization of applied N is high in sodic soils. We are experimenting with timing and N splits to match the plant needs, slow-release fertilizers, deep placement, and urease inhibitors to improve urea efficiency.

In a field experiment in 1984 wet season, we evaluated the efficiency of prilled urea applied all at once (PUW) prilled urea applied in split doses (PUS), one-half at transplanting, one-fourth at 21 d after transplanting (DT) and one-fourth at 42 DT; sulfur-coated urea (SCU), 37.4% N; lac-coated urea (LCU), 30.4% N; and urea 1-g supergranules (USG). All were applied at 120 kg N/ha.

Soil was sodic sandy loam, Calciorthid Natrustalf, pH 8.4, EC